

Modelling stability at microscale, both within and above the atmospheric boundary layer, substantially improves wind speed predictions

James Bleeg, Dnyanesh Digaskar, Ulrik Horn, Jean-François Corbett
james.bleeg@dnvgl.com, Tel: +44 117 972 9900, Fax: +44 117 972 9901
DNV GL, One Linear Park, Avon Street, Bristol BS2 0PS, UK.

Summary: Despite growing recognition of its importance, atmospheric stability and its pronounced impact on wind flow over topography remain a challenge for the wind industry. Slowing progress is a lack of agreement on the extent to which stability can affect wind speeds and how to account for stability within wind flow analyses. As a result, the widespread adoption of microscale wind flow models that adequately account for atmospheric stability has yet to occur. According to field measurements and numerical experiments presented in this paper, diurnal stability variation within the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) has a substantial impact on the spatial variation of the wind resource over a wide variety of locations and terrain types. The same is true of the stable stratification that commonly occurs in the troposphere above the ABL. This stratification influences the thickness of the ABL. In other words, it restricts and controls the area through which the boundary layer fluid flows, which in turn can have a first-order impact on wind speed at turbine heights. We account for these key influences within an efficient CFD model described herein. We applied this model to 57 wind sites spread across 13 countries on 6 continents and compared the results with on-site measurements, yielding 1162 comparisons between CFD-predicted and measurement-derived mean wind speed values. The CFD results were further benchmarked against WAsP, an industry standard, linear flow model. This extensive global validation demonstrates that rigorously accounting for atmospheric stability within a microscale CFD model yields substantial accuracy gains.

1 INTRODUCTION

Despite recent advances, wind flow modelling remains one of the largest sources of uncertainty for pre-construction wind energy production assessments. Many have correctly pointed to atmospheric stability and its absence from some of the most widely used microscale flow models as a primary cause of significant discrepancies between wind speed predictions and observations in the field [1],[2],[3]. How and to what degree atmospheric stability influences the wind resource is not, however, well understood within the wind industry. Nor is there consensus on how to implement stability into a microscale wind flow model or even what aspects of stability need to be accounted for [1],[4],[5],[6],[7]. Using a combination of modelling and measurements, this paper identifies aspects of atmospheric stability that have a large impact on the spatial variation of the wind resource; it also describes how these aspects should be accounted for within a microscale wind flow analysis.

We focus specifically on modelling stable stratification, both within and above the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL). Wind speed measurements in areas of heavy wind development around the world reveal that the spatial variation of the wind resource at an on-shore wind site can change significantly with boundary layer stability. Mast-to-mast wind speed ratios derived from measurements at a wind site in Sweden illustrate the issue. As can be seen in Figure 1, the wind speed ratios, or speedups, are quite different during statically stable conditions as compared to unstable/neutral conditions. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and measurements are used in [1] and [8] to show that significant improvements in wind speed prediction accuracy can be achieved when the wind flow model accounts for the stability variation within the boundary layer.

Figure 1 – Speedups between two meteorological masts at an on-shore wind site in Sweden. The speedups are derived from measurements binned by direction sector and static stability.

The impact of stability in the free atmosphere on wind speeds near the ground is also addressed in the literature. Montavon et al [9] reported that accounting for stable stratification in the free atmosphere in a CFD model reduced mean wind speed cross-prediction errors substantially at a site with three meteorological masts. Vosper [10] used idealized, two-dimensional, numerical simulations to show how stable stratification in the free atmosphere and inversion layer dramatically affects flow near the ground.

Despite these findings, atmospheric stability is still frequently neglected or insufficiently accounted for in wind farm scale flow modelling. This paper seeks to convey to the industry a greater appreciation for the extent to which stable stratification can impact the spatial variation of wind speeds over a wide variety of terrain—as well as physical insight into why it has such a large impact. To this end, we interrogate CFD flow solutions over idealized terrain, with and without stability. We then report results from an extensive global validation demonstrating the predictive accuracy of a microscale CFD model that rigorously accounts for atmospheric stability within and above the ABL.

2 MODEL

We use steady-state RANS (Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes) calculations in this study to simulate wind flow over topography. The simulations were setup in accordance with DNV GL's latest methodology and executed using STAR-CCM+, a commercial CFD software package from CD-adapco. The RANS equations were closed with the $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence model. In addition, we reformulated the governing equations using the shallow Boussinesq approach in order to account for buoyancy. In the shallow Boussinesq approach, the flow is incompressible (i.e., the divergence of velocity equals 0), and the effect of density variations on the momentum equation are neglected except in the gravity term [11]. This approach is considered appropriate when the vertical length scale of the flow is much less than the density scale height, which is typically on the order of 8 km. Details of the governing equations are in [1].

After establishing the governing equations, boundary conditions are the key to representing atmospheric stability in a RANS model. Specifically, the vertical variation of potential temperature defines the static stability. Figure 2 shows example potential temperature profiles over land

corresponding to a convective boundary layer in the daytime and a stable boundary layer during the night. The atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) is a little over 1 km thick in this example.

Figure 2 – Example potential temperature profiles in the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) and the free atmosphere (FA), during the day (red) and at night (blue). Hypothetical, completely neutral atmospheric conditions are also represented (black dashed).

In dealing with diurnal stability variations at a given on-shore wind site, we used a similar approach to that described in [1]. In this approach simulations of the neutral boundary layer (potential temperature is constant within the boundary layer) are used to represent neutral and unstable conditions at the site; simulations of a stable boundary layer (potential temperature increases with height within the boundary layer) are used to represent stable conditions. The two sets of calculations are then combined using weighting factors derived from on-site measurements in order to produce a single overall wind speed representation for the site. The inflow boundary conditions (wind speed vector, turbulence, and potential temperature) within the stable boundary layer are defined using established similarity theories for the equilibrium nocturnal boundary layer [1]. The neutral boundary layer is defined using [12].

We also account for the stable stratification that typically occurs above the ABL. The boundary conditions in this study feature a capping inversion with a maximum potential temperature gradient of +10 K/km and a free atmosphere with a vertical potential temperature gradient of +3.3 K/km, which is consistent with the lapse rate of an International Standard Atmosphere within the troposphere. The uniform stratification extends to the top of the domain approximately 17 km above mean ground level. Turbulence, wind speed, and wind direction are also specified to be constant at the inflow boundaries above the ABL.

The potential temperature increases more than 50 K from the ground to the top of the domain. This large variation required us to replace the Boussinesq model built into STAR-CCM+, which employed a reference state corresponding to a constant potential temperature. Employing user-defined source terms we re-wrote the buoyancy terms in the governing equations relative to a hydrostatic reference state that can vary with altitude. The rewritten model was verified using the

same benchmark cases reported in [1]. Included in these benchmarks are cases verifying that the inflow boundary conditions are horizontally homogeneous over flat terrain with uniform roughness.

3 IDEALIZED TERRAIN

In this section we show CFD results for flow over idealized terrain in order to illustrate how accounting for various aspects of stability affects wind speed predictions. The three geometries investigated are a tall 2D hill, a tall 3D hill, and a short 2D hill.

Figure 3 – CFD-predicted flow over the tall 2D hill. Top: Normalized wind speed 80 m above ground level (a.g.l.) from a purely neutral simulation (red line) and a neutral boundary layer (BL) simulation with stable stratification in the free atmosphere (SIFA) (blue line). Middle: Same as Top, but the wind speed is normalized at the top of the hill. Bottom: The tall 2D hill profile (black) as well as the bounding streamlines for the boundary layers (dashed).

The tall 2D hill is a “Witch of Agnesi” with a height of 240 m and a half-height, half-width of 2100 m. Flow over this 2D hill was simulated within a 3D domain measuring 60 km x 40 km x 17 km. The near-ground wind direction is parallel to the x-axis and perpendicular to the 2D hill in the middle of the lower boundary of the domain. Figure 3 shows results for two types of flow over this hill: a purely neutral flow representing the traditional CFD approach and a neutral boundary layer with stable

stratification in the free atmosphere (SIFA). We normalize the wind speed traces to the wind speeds predicted at both the inlet (Figure 3, Top) and the top of the hill (Figure 3, Middle). Normalizing to the inlet presents an accessible picture of the wind speed trends while normalizing at the top of the hill better represents how the flow model results is typically used—to predict the wind speeds relative to a meteorological tower set atop an elevated feature.

Accounting for SIFA in the CFD analysis significantly affects the wind speed variation at a typical turbine hub height. Specifically, it substantially increases the wind speed at the top of the hill relative to the surrounding terrain. An exception is on the lee side of the hill, where relative to the top of the hill the SIFA calculation predicts higher wind speeds than the traditional, pure neutral approach (Figure 3, Middle). An explanation for the SIFA vs. pure neutral trends is evident in an analysis of the boundary layer thickness. The boundary layer in the SIFA result is much thinner at the top of the hill and just downstream as compared to over the surrounding terrain. This squeezing of the boundary layer speeds up the flow in these locations relative to areas where the boundary layer is thicker. In the pure neutral CFD results, the boundary layer rises substantially when traveling over the hill. So while the boundary layer still thins relative to the surrounding areas, the thinning is much less pronounced than in the SIFA result. In the SIFA simulation the fluid in the boundary layer is much denser than the fluid above and therefore cannot as easily be perturbed by terrain into the much lighter free atmosphere.

Figure 4 – CFD-predicted flow over the tall 2D hill. Top: Normalized wind speed 80 m a.g.l. from a purely neutral simulation (red), a neutral BL simulation with SIFA (blue), and a stable BL simulation with SIFA (purple). Bottom: The tall 2D hill profile (black)

Stable stratification within the boundary layer causes wind speed predictions to deviate further from the calculation of a purely neutral atmosphere. Figure 4 shows results for a simulation of a stable boundary layer with SIFA (magenta) over the tall 2D hill, along with results from the pure neutral simulation and neutral boundary layer with SIFA simulation shown in Figure 3. The stable boundary layer corresponds to an Obukhov length of 148 m, and the change in potential temperature from the ground to the residual layer is 4.9 K. Including this stratification within the boundary layer reduces

wind speed on the upstream side of the hill and significantly increases it on the downstream side relative to the other simulations. The waves evident in the near-ground wind speed traces from both SIFA simulations are due to gravity waves in the uniformly-stratified free atmosphere. These gravity waves are evident in Figure 5.

Figure 5 – Vertical component of velocity plotted on a constant y-plane, which is roughly parallel to the direction of the flow near the ground. The boundary layer is stable and the free atmosphere is uniformly stably stratified (same case as the purple line in Figure 4).

Simulating flow perpendicular to a 2D hill amplifies the impact of SIFA to a degree, but the results are still quite sensitive to stability when simulating flow over 3D terrain. Figure 6 shows results from flow over an axisymmetric Witch of Agnesi with the same geometric parameters as was used for the 2D hill in Figure 4. Going from a 2D to a 3D hill slightly diminishes the impact of accounting for SIFA, though the impact of stratification in the boundary layer appears to be just as large.

Figure 6 – CFD-predicted flow over the tall 3D hill. Top: Normalized wind speed 80 m a.g.l. from a purely neutral simulation (red), a neutral BL simulation with SIFA (blue), and a stable BL simulation with SIFA (purple). Bottom: The tall 3D hill peak profile (black)

Accounting for stability above and within the ABL also has a material impact on the predicted spatial variation of wind speed over simple terrain. Figure 7 shows results from flow simulations over the short 2D hill. The hill is also derived from the “Witch of Agnesi” geometry, but with a height of 60 m and a half-height, half-width of 3500 m. The terrain is gently sloping with a maximum inclination of 0.6 degrees. Flow over this hill was simulated within a 50 km x 40 km x 17 km domain. The near-ground wind direction is parallel to the x-axis and perpendicular to the 2D hill in the middle of the lower boundary of the domain. As with the tall 2D hill, accounting for SIFA increases the contrast between the wind speeds near the top of the hill and the surrounding terrain. Stability within the ABL again reduces the predicted wind speed upstream of the hill and increases it downstream.

Figure 7 – CFD-predicted flow over the short 2D hill. Top: Normalized wind speed 80 m a.g.l. from a purely neutral simulation (red), a neutral BL simulation with SIFA (blue), and a stable BL simulation with SIFA (purple). Bottom: The short 2D hill profile (black)

4 COMPARISON WITH FIELD MEASUREMENTS

The CFD model described herein was used to analyse 57 wind sites spread across 13 countries and 6 continents. Each of these sites had multiple meteorological masts where wind speed measurements were taken prior to turbine construction. From these measurements, long term wind speed and direction frequency distributions were derived for the mast locations at hub height. Converting to long term distributions often involved correlating with sources of long term wind data, and estimating these distributions at hub height usually included extrapolating from or interpolating between measurement heights. Thus, these distributions included uncertainties associated not only with the measurements, but also data processing/analysis. This added noise to the analysis of the flow modelling errors. Nevertheless, these long term distributions were used for this study because they were readily available from our commercial analyses, thus providing a very large validation set to which we can compare model predictions. The validation set includes every site with at least two masts where we have run this upgraded CFD model—no sites were filtered out.

At each site we ran approximately 60 steady-state CFD simulations, each one corresponding to a different combination of wind direction and stability class (i.e. neutral boundary layer or stable

boundary layer). On-site measurements informed the spacing and total number of simulated directions. From the results we derived predicted speedups between mast locations at hub height for each of 12 direction sectors.

The predicted 12-sector speedups between a reference mast and a target mast can be applied to the speed and direction distributions derived from measurements at the reference mast in order to predict the long term mean wind speed (MWS) at the target mast. The predicted long term MWS can then be easily compared with the MWS derived from measurements at the target mast. This process was repeated for every possible mast pair combination in the validation set, yielding 1162 comparisons between CFD-predicted and measurement-derived MWS values.

A natural benchmark for these CFD simulations, which account for stability within and above the boundary layer, would be CFD simulations that do not account for stability. Producing another full set of simulations for all of these sites, however, would be onerous, so instead the linear WAsP model was used as a benchmark. WAsP offers very fast turnaround and enough accuracy to remain an industry standard. The WAsP model does not account for atmospheric stability, aside for a minor correction to vertical profiles of wind speeds according to specified surface heat fluxes.

Figure 8 – %RMS error on MWS predictions at each of 57 wind sites, CFD vs. WAsP.

At each wind site, we compiled all the mast-to-mast prediction errors and computed a root mean square (RMS) error for CFD and an RMS error for WAsP. The RMS errors are summarized in Figure 8. For points below the black diagonal line, CFD offers better MWS predictions than WAsP at that site. The farther below the black diagonal line the point sits, the more accurate CFD is relative

to WAsP—vice versa for points above the line. 85% of the points are below the diagonal line, with many of the points well below this line. There is only one point well above the black diagonal line, and it corresponds to a site with only two masts. The average of the RMS errors is 2.6% for CFD and 4.4% for WAsP, which is a substantial difference, particularly when one considers that the errors include the not-insignificant uncertainty in the measurement-based values.

This large improvement was achieved despite using the same set of parameters at each site to define the stratification above the boundary layer. In fact, these parameters—the average lapse rate in the free atmosphere, for example—vary across the globe [13], and the CFD results can be sensitive to their levels. The use of site-specific stratification derived from mesoscale model output and/or radiosonde measurements may further improve CFD accuracy.

In order to highlight the impact of accounting for stability in CFD wind flow analyses, additional CFD calculations were run at three European sites—in France, Poland, and Sweden. These sites had 3, 3, and 4 masts, respectively. Figure 9 summarizes the results. Four types of predictions were made: linear WAsP (black), CFD with stability neglected (red), CFD accounting for stability in the free atmosphere but not the ABL (blue), and CFD accounting for stability in the free atmosphere and the ABL (purple). Accounting for stability in the free atmosphere increased CFD accuracy at each of the three sites. Modelling stability variation in the boundary layer increased accuracy further.

Figure 9 – %RMS error on mean wind speed predictions at three sites in Europe. Results are from four models: linear WAsP (black), CFD with stability neglected (red), CFD accounting for stability in the free atmosphere but not the ABL (blue), and CFD accounting for stability in the free atmosphere and stability variation in the ABL (red).

“CFD” has become a blanket term used to refer to a highly disparate zoo of models that are set up and run in a wide variety of different ways, not all of which are physically and numerically appropriate in the context of wind farm scale simulations; and so it is not legitimately possible to draw conclusions about the accuracy of CFD in general using results from a single CFD model. For example, in a number of conferences, most recently here [14], Beaucage *et al.* have highlighted higher errors from CFD as compared to WAsP. The errors were calculated from predictions of mean wind speed at 9 selected sites. Atmospheric stability, however, was not accounted for in their CFD calculations. In [2] they nominally tested the impact of stability on the CFD results with little impact

on accuracy reported, but the CFD model they used lacked a gravity term in the momentum equation, severely limiting the ability of the model to account for stability. In light of the results shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9, it is reasonable to conclude that the authors of [2] and [14] would have come to a much different finding had they used a CFD approach that rigorously accounted for atmospheric stability. CFD can be a powerful and accurate tool for a myriad of applications, but its effective use requires the careful accounting of the dominant physical influences, without which quite unreasonable results are likely to be obtained.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Modelling and measurements show that stratification within and above the atmospheric boundary layer has a significant impact on the spatial variation of the wind resource. Without accounting for these controlling physics, it is not possible for a microscale wind flow model to consistently produce reliable wind speed predictions. An extensive global validation shows, however, that atmospheric stability can be effectively accounted for within a steady-state microscale CFD model, allowing for the generation of much more accurate wind speed predictions within the time frame of a typical energy production assessment.

6 REFERENCES

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